

Economic Empowerment of Students Through Entrepreneurship Training at the Manahijussadat Modern Islamic Boarding School

Devi Aulia Hidayati ^{1*} Adam Hafidz Al Fajar ² Bima Fandi Asy'arie ³
Khoirul Taufiq ⁴

^{1,2,4} Universitas Islam Negeri Raden Intan Lampung

³ Universitas Islam Negeri Malik Ibrahim Malang

Corresponding Author: Adam Hafidz Al Fajar Hafidzalazharie@gmail.com

ARTICLE INFO

Keywords: Manahijussadat, Education, Training

Received : 02 September

Revised : 06 October

Accepted: 08 November

©2023 Hidayati , Fajar, Asy'arie, Taufiq : This is an open-access article distributed under the terms of the [Creative Commons Atribusi 4.0 Internasional](https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/).

ABSTRACT

Manahijussadat Modern Islamic boarding school is an educational establishment that promotes contemporary Islamic teachings. The school incorporates an entrepreneurship program aimed at both male and female students. A research initiative was conducted to elucidate the entrepreneurship empowerment strategies employed by the Modern Manahijussadat Lebak Banten Islamic boarding school. The research adopted a descriptive qualitative approach, gathering comprehensive data from observations, interviews, and documentation. Thirteen participants were selected using a purposive sampling technique. Data collection involved the use of observation, interviews, and documentation methods. The study's findings highlight ongoing efforts to empower student entrepreneurship, particularly in the cottage industry sector, including the provision of education and training.

INTRODUCTION

According to Aprilia Theresia (2015) santri entrepreneurship is basically the beginning of the word This is interpreted through the two words mentioned for explain the meaning of student entrepreneurship itself in its separation, it is entrepreneurship accompanied by santri The broad meaning explained regarding entrepreneurship is understanding that serves to carry out an assessment of various things that improve and bring about change which refers to the increasing enthusiasm of various Innovation and having the courage to be responsible be responsible for any risks that will be discovered during the follow-up the work process itself and its main goal so that it can be achieved realizing the creation of certain works. based on opinion basrowi the word entrepreneurship itself is a word taken from the absorption of the meaning of Wira accompanied by effort. with In other words, he is called a hero or an individual who has excellence, getting role models, having commendable behavior what is done, has noble and other characteristics etc. while to interpret the word business itself interpreted in other words as action, work accompanying the process of community empowerment, it is the community who are the actors and determinants of development.

While referring to Muhammad Anwar (2014) said the word entrepreneurship was taken from an original borrowing of the word it is entrepreneurship and it is an integration of several words which are then interpreted in one meaning then The separation is hero and business. the meaning of rainy itself can be mentioned as a man who had a dashing nature and Officer. while to interpret the word business is actions, efforts and so on that are referred to to be able to realized accompanied by energy in the process This will link to the implementation of various actions which is realized based on the energy given, then interpretation of the level of criticism expressed by thoughts in order to realize the desired goals realized. In this way, entrepreneurship is considered as a form of warrior who carries out certain things.

Islamic boarding schools are made into one of the institutions which is so big that of course has great potential and function continues to experience growth in the level of entrepreneurship are in Indonesia. therefore, Islamic boarding schools already exist was during the colonial period which followed various models modern applications are known even in the education taught or enforced in an agency does not include only religion but also things of a general nature so even though the development of globalization is so rapid, it can continue creating potential. So close to such a significant development towards Islamic boarding schools experienced such a spread widespread especially in Indonesia and this has a function The main thing is that all individuals can be empowered and utilized in such a way that it can be realized The original goal was to operate within an educational institution religion-based, prioritizes da'wah values, is within aspects of general society accompanied by others. Which trying to keep up with changes over time and continue experienced an increase in the birth of a nation has good potential.

Entrepreneurship that continues to be implemented with purpose can follow any form that is attempted towards In this Islamic boarding school, there are many levels of stages that will be passed such as improving one's abilities owned, then Jasmine various businesses in it with cooperative interpretation and so on. efforts made by Islamic boarding schools with the aim of being able to create various young generations who not only understand religion but it can also be useful in a continuing society experienced a surge in concomitant economic improvement with the development of the times that will be formed in the country Indonesia. then also used as a basic form for every society with the aim of changing lives individual and this will carry out an evaluation stage moving towards the economic sector, then industry, agriculture, and so forth. Islamic boarding schools are one of the many areas which continue to be covered has the potential to give birth to various young generations especially the Manahijussadat Islamic boarding school which is in progress Founded on November 21, 1996, entrepreneurship too used as a support for what will be taught towards all individuals and this is determined based on Mr Drs.k. Sulaiman Effendi MPDI will be followed by a number of students and female students who are within this scope are worth 300 individual. Manahijussadat Islamic boarding school Rangkasbitung Lebak Banten used as one of the many Islamic boarding schools Of course, it has certain relevant purposes integrating various combinations of knowledge both in nature general or religious which is considered important to both. of the two sciences mentioned thus are applied to each individual in the Islamic boarding school manahijussadat is one of the many developments This is related to entrepreneurship which functions for carry out management of the efforts carried out by all parties, and this will conform to the regulations of religion itself. Entrepreneurial skills that reside precisely in the cottage Manahijussadat Islamic boarding school is used as a potential one which will be useful in the future and make life The individual can be in the midst of society though along with the development of the influence of globalization which continues to determine whether individuals can improve their economy There is.

The entrepreneurship that is built certainly has a purpose especially in Islamic boarding schools manahijussadat which means all students will get it completed his education in the area then able to give himself to the circle of space scope to remain able to follow the flow of behavioral patterns the lives of other individuals in which it will also be fulfill all forms of financial needs to the economy that will pass, even this is made as the main capital that individuals must have for broadens his knowledge and broadens his knowledge implemented in order to advance your career path in the future that he has. entrepreneurship in the aspect of empowerment which is carried out especially in Islamic boarding schools manahijussadat can be applied in various aspects such as sirkah Putra, Putri, bookshop, male canteen, female, mall colors, male or female kiosk, male or female laundry, bakery, Manahij graphy, credit and Barbershop.

There are efforts being made towards the cottage Manahijussadat Islamic boarding school with the aim of obtaining separate levels for each individual to

continue pursuing entrepreneurship through which there is training which is implemented then followed by the motivation that is owned for example, it will be interpreted through the general stage which is related to successful entrepreneurs of course.

Field facts related to the goodness of cooperative programs Pondok, namely ongoing activities, has reached 80%, this due to efforts to maximize availability of the resources that will be utilized for coverage certain areas that are within the scope of Islamic boarding schools as such will indicate the presence of stimulation that will Create various other businesses and gain levels One of the advantages is that it is interpreted through savings and loans, cottage minimarket, and refillable water running until now. Other programs that are running well are: is Book Shop, in this program the goal is almost close to 96% of this is motivated by continuous books experiencing such high sales will continue to run due to ongoing needs and the parties who continues to publish these various books experienced an increase and dissemination of figures who he has. After a period of 3 months there was a visit from the publisher who wanted to check the books that had run out sold and there are still unsold remains.

The pattern of such determination is from a financial aspect which was so dominant in the initial coverage is not the case consider it to be the most needed aspect. through the computer that will perform the actions related to financial bookkeeping carried out from stage to stage The running process is simple to explain How cash continues to have an influence, both from the reception aspect or quite the opposite. basically that coverage, of course has a form of obligation that must be fulfilled within its implementation. marketing efforts towards the availability of various books specifically for those included in within the internal scope of students can be fulfilled. Based on the availability of the number of individuals who take it Education among these people has an obligation applies to purchasing stationery others who come from such places. through levels the type of marketing that is protective means that efforts are made applied which is also interpreted through the shop books will continue to synergize with each other so that it is also followed in line with the growth that occurs towards Islamic boarding schools. The last one is the Manahijussadat restaurant, program This is already happening with almost 90% of the existing field facts, namely, This restaurant has opened catering and invites students to join as well as helping sales of cottage restaurants, many students The daughter who likes cooking makes this restaurant quite advanced and known by the public because it always has innovation new to attract customers.

Based on observations in the surrounding area Cottage, researchers found universally towards the public there are predictions put forward regarding those who studying at an Islamic boarding school will definitely only understand just about religious knowledge. but from the development of the times continues to require individuals to apply various other knowledge in each institution, especially in any education which is also applied in Islamic boarding schools, not only studying science Only religion is obtained for

students, but skills and mindset It is the students who can create students who are not only knowledgeable religious knowledge only.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Entrepreneurship Empowerment Theory

According to Karjuni Dt, Maani (2018) actor theory explains that it is related to empowerment mentioned from Sarah cook and mancualy With the perspective put forward towards the public becomes part of the subject at the moment carry out various changes over the stages who carries out the release from the other party experiencing restraining control there is a party given to refer to degree of freedom in order to resolve obligations for the various formulations put forward with certain considerations of policy and his actions. according to the directions expressed by their views on empowerment to delegation in nature social and prioritize various aspects has noble values that prioritize morals as The main requirement is to encourage of the patience you have, and carry it out according to social authority, giving regulation of the level of work produced, enable organizations to experience change leads to progress, whether local or, on the contrary, extra, organizing cooperation, providing a level of communication is efficient and effective, providing support in the form of creativity in order to find solutions appropriate answers to the various problems found.

By using this type of empowerment offered. Thus, there is a review who made the plans that have been obtained experienced changes in its use had been anticipated in such a way The output obtained has the capability of power maximum use, this concept can stated in two forms of premises major, namely failure or adjustment against Hope, failure in other words is called as a use of various models implemented in order to improve the economy who have failed so that they can solve the problem in order anticipate the occurrence of poverty among ongoing and periodic public, while Hope itself is an effort which continues to experience continuation and is considered as an alternative which is also provided in the framework carry out development and input various forms of democratic values in their application, there is a level of gender equality, various a generation that has equality and holds improvement in financial aspects sufficient. these two aspects are not included as a benchmark for various social sciences but the real form obtained from normative and moral determinations whose nature originates from real on individuals and the public.

Social Learning Theory in Community Empowerment

In this research the author uses provisions that establish social learning theory. For explains it, namely carrying out various activities carried out by individuals in order to hold changes to overall behavior towards a learning process that follows various changes experienced and in this case related to aspects of skills, then skills and behavior stated, defining and determining dignity and dignity, character, adaptation, etc. based on The explanation above means a more inherent understanding Learning itself is considered an effort

which is consciously carried out by individuals with various experiences gained and followed through certain training in order to gain potential specific and recent nature that creates that behavior possessions are subject to change and character staying is part of the impact of the training held by Islamic boarding schools:

1. Stages of social learning learning

Bandura (1997) defines self-efficacy as an individual's belief in their capacity to organize and execute a series of actions necessary to accomplish a specific task. This belief, he asserts, results from the interplay between external circumstances, self-regulatory mechanisms, personal capabilities, experiences, and education. Gufron and Risnawati (2016) echo this sentiment, explaining self-efficacy as a cognitive process involving decision-making or expectations about one's ability to undertake tasks and achieve desired outcomes. According to Lunenburg in Sebayang (2017) adds that self-efficacy is an inner conviction within an individual, enabling them to confront and resolve challenges in various situations while effectively strategizing and surmounting obstacles to achieve desired objectives. Alwisol, as cited in Renaningtyas (2017), defines self-efficacy as an individual's perception of their ability to function in accordance with the demands of a given situation. Bandura, as referenced in Renaningtyas (2017), portrays self-efficacy as an individual's confidence in their capacity to exert control over themselves, their roles, and environmental events to the best of their abilities.

Self-efficacy carries out various forms of action which has an impact in line with expectations, various This process is regulated in the above learning activities

modeling aspects are:

- a. Make observations that are referenced to the model what is contained in it always does wasteful arrangement of personal. that attention given the individual should refer to models of certain conditions and various elements. if such concerns cannot be referred to by the individual suitable for the use of this model indicates imitation or plagiarism efforts could not be realized. various types of factors which functions to strengthen sensory capacities and so on to the conditions that form it model provisions and serve as the background the main stages of this attention to Students.
- b. Which representation in making observations to put forward responses, various patterns certain things that are realized by symbolic determination found in a memory. various stages in storing according to characteristics the most important of certain conditions With This will be mentioned repeatedly and used when needed. storage These characteristics are of course interpreted through codes that make it easier for us in conducting trials of actions which is interpreted symbolically.
- c. The behavior obtained will refer to presentation of attention in the use of the model anything and strengthen everything have been observed, will form certain behavior for his achievements. from a physical aspect there is

abilities possessed by individuals carry out the determination of such action.

- d. Motivation and reinforcement are linked to learning system that is pursued in order make clear observations known subject used during the follow-up the learning process for students is motivated That is what is meant in the model. although observations made on other parties, of course provide teaching during implementation various things but have no inner will carry out various behaviors as needed. encouragement obtained through reinforcement, namely a party whose role is to carry out observations in order to produce model behavior as well get this by direct connection. but which is indirect if in interpret vicarious reinforcement. reference to the behavior of another party for observer at the time of his review followed by behavioral production is growing. as well as interpretation through self-reinforcement and doing personal control. the form is relevant especially for companions and internal students implement it.

In order to determine the various stages In modeling, observation trends are obtained in accordance with the encouragement of the stated expectations permanent top modeling in the other party who does imitation to achieve such reinforcement, In determination to adapt to learning referring to other parties for reinforcement or precisely punishment resulting from participation is in accordance with the action thereby. therefore in this deception we use four stages which have been interpreted as follows when carrying out entrepreneurial empowerment towards all parties in the Islamic boarding school Modern Manahijussadat Lebak Banten. Based on Bandura's opinion (2017), there is the gains obtained from learning activities on the availability of information obtained from observations and various forms of consequences are accepted accordingly by personal actions or other parties. info Useful observation of any aspect with adapt to all necessary aspects. Matter This is because it is personal behavior and other parties who are able to produce reinforcement and can anticipate the provisions of the punishment that will be applied through its functional nature, thus many various actions such tendencies make observations first to obtain and remembered according to a provision of memory and used next time. The importance of the gains made during following the study of certain observations will include levels of attention in it, also the placement and ability aspects of behavior and etc. thus if it is deep carrying out observational learning, this incident was not found, this is based on his opinion Himself, the activities carried out by Him are not is relevant to the use of the model, or not able to direct his memory to determine in memory and so on to do it.

2. Processes That Influence Learning Observational

a. Attentional Process

Occurrence model of affective valence prominence complexity of prevalence value function, where occurrence model as an attribute of ability

observers perceptual set perceptual cognitive ability level the emergence of acquired preferences.

b. Retention Process

Symbolic coding of cognitive organization cognitive rehearsal implementation rehearsal, where model events as observer attributes cognitive skills cognitive structure.

c. Production process

Representation of observations of the implementation of information conception adjustment feedback, where the incident model as an observer attribute of physical abilities component sub-skills.

d. Motivational Process

Sensory external incentives are visibly social control of various self-incentives is visible in evaluation self, in the event of the model as an observer standard social comparative bias incentive preferences internal.

Entrepreneurship Indicators

According to Manab and Abdul (2021), an entrepreneurship program can be said to be good, if the program has run as expected expected. The following are the characteristics of an entrepreneurship program This has been going well, including:

1. The program is running according to its objectives
2. The program is running according to plan
3. Increase in the number of entrepreneurial interests
4. Increased community satisfaction

METHODOLOGY

Provide clear and concise versions of your methods of conducting research, population and samples, and data analysis tools. This research uses qualitative research.

This research uses data expressed verbally and the qualifications are theoretical. According to Marzuki (2005) data processing and hypothesis testing are not based on statistics, but on certain legal patterns according to the laws of logic. Qualitative research utilizes field data to verify theories that arise in the field and are continuously refined during the direct research process which is carried out repeatedly. Apart from that, qualitative research is research that uses a natural setting which aims to interpret phenomena that occur and have been carried out using various existing methods.

In this research, the author collected data by coming directly to the research location, namely at the Manahijussadat Lebak Banten Islamic Boarding School. The author interacted face to face with the Ustadz and the Santri. The author collected the data himself, the data was obtained from various sources, the researcher processed the themes into a series of complete themes, the researcher focused on studying the meaning conveyed by the participants, the

research process developed dynamically according to conditions in the field, the researcher used a theoretical perspective, especially the perspective of women's empowerment, the researcher interpret findings in the field, and provide a complex picture of study.

This research was conducted at the Manahijussadat Lebak Banten Islamic Boarding School, and also involved Ustadz and Santri. The population is the entire research object. Population research is carried out if the researcher wants to see all the intricacies in the population. So the population is the total number of research subjects that has not been limited, as is the case with sampling which has been limited to the total population. Population in

This research consisted of administrators totaling 10 people, consisting of 4 Class 6A students from 2 students and 2 female students, then 3 people consisting of class 6B students, namely 1 Santriwan and 2 female students, and 3 people consisting of class 6C, namely 2 Santriwan and 1 female student. The selection of participants in this research used the Purposive Sampling technique, namely a sampling technique by determining certain criteria. So in this participant research are as follows:

1. Head of the Manahijussadat Modern Islamic Boarding School, numbering 1 person with the criteria; he is the leader who has authority and policy in development within the Manahijussadat Islamic boarding school, namely Mr. K.H Sulaiman
2. The Head of the Business Unit consists of 1 person with the following criteria: the person in charge of leading and coordinating the entrepreneurship sector at the Manahijussadat Islamic boarding school, namely Mr. ustaz Darman
3. Entrepreneurship companion is counted as one individual and the requirements that are met are that they have fully understood and referred to the provision of various forms of material that will be applied during training on entrepreneurship from students who are the parties who will benefit from these activities while the determination of one individual is used as availability. The data source is Ustad Asep..
4. Entrepreneurial members from the availability of students range 10 individuals. which is a form of requirement that can be fulfilled is that he has carried out training on entrepreneurship, getting control then the empowerment process Santri entrepreneurship, the participants were 4 people consisting of class students (6A) consisting of 2 students and 2 female students, then 3 students consisting of class 6B students from 1 female student and 2 female students, finally 3 class members 6C consists of 2 female students and 1 female student. Based on the various criteria that have been mentioned, the determination of participants who will be used in the research activities carried out is around 13 individuals who in this interpretation were found to be leaders of the Modern Islamic Boarding School Manahijussadat.

One of the important steps in research is the data collection process. To obtain appropriate and relevant data and information, the author used several research methods, namely observation, interviews and documentation.

The data validity tests in this research include data credibility tests, transferability tests, dependability tests, and confirmability tests. In this research, researchers used a credibility test to test the validity of the data. Testing the credibility of the data was carried out by triangulation. Data triangulation is defined as checking data from various sources in various ways and at various times. There are 3 triangulations in data validity, namely source triangulation, technique triangulation and time triangulation. In this study, researchers used source triangulation. Source triangulation is testing the validity of data by checking data that has been obtained through several sources. Triangulation of sources will be carried out by Ustadz and Santri.

RESEARCH RESULT

The empowerment programs implemented at the Manahijussadat modern Islamic boarding school include cottage cooperatives, cottage canteens, Manahij bread, animal husbandry, fish farming, warrahmah, Manahij graphics, bookshops and Manahij restaurants. The empowerment process in Islamic boarding schools can be described in a table like the following:

Table 1. Entrepreneurship program at the Manahijussadat Modern Islamic boarding school

NO	Nama Program	Jenis	Pelatih
1	Cottage Cooperative	Providing Equipment Santri	Mr. Darman
2	Cottage Canteen	Food and Drink	Mr. Sapriadi
3	Manahij Bread	Toast and Donuts	Mr. Awan Abdul
4	Farm	Goats, Cows and Chickens	Mr. Gilang Septian
5	Fish cultivation	Catfish and Tilapia	Mrs. Nurhalina
6	Warrahmah	Charity Stall	Mrs. Werdiatina
7	Manahij Graphics	Photography, design and screen printing	Mrs. Ununnayah
8	Bookshop	Textbooks	Mrs. Nisamazidah
9	Manahij Resto	Chicken and fried chicken	Mr. Alwi Sihabudin

a. Empowering Santri Entrepreneurship

Islamic boarding schools as Islamic scientific institutions in everyday life focus on the importance of religious morals which are practiced as a guide for daily attitudes and behavior. The empowerment of students began in 2017, precisely in February. This empowerment is motivated by students who live simple lives and are less fortunate. Some of the programs that have been running to date are the cottage cooperative, bookshop and Manahij restaurant. facts on the ground regarding this empowerment program have been running by optimizing the use of existing resources.

Based on this, Islamic boarding school managers certainly have efforts to develop student entrepreneurship, so that many students at the modern Islamic boarding school Manahijussadat Lebak Banten are interested in taking part in entrepreneurship. One of the efforts of Islamic boarding school management is entrepreneurship training. This entrepreneurship training is through programs that are currently running well, namely: the boarding school cooperative, Manahij restaurant and bookshop. This is in accordance with what was conveyed by the ustaz, namely: "*The management here creates entrepreneurial programs to attract the interest of students, so there is already a platform that suits the needs of the students.*"

b. Empowerment of Pondok Cooperative Santri Entrepreneurship

Based on the results of interviews conducted with the ustaz as the cottage manager, the efforts made include providing education and training. Before the students implemented Santi, they were given education regarding the activities in the field of Islamic boarding school cooperatives, this was in accordance with what was conveyed by the Ustad, namely: "*Before going directly, we will first tell you about the activities. activities and sub-sectors in the cooperative*". Not only that, the ustaz also provides training to the students, in this training the ustaz continues to accompany the students and continues to provide direction to the students. The implementation of various stages to carry out training must be empowered. So it starts with the management team whose role is to prepare all these things, to be able to create certain groups according to the efforts carried out in a simultaneous manner so that they are able to realize a legal form of interpretation. each member's type of membership as a whole for the Islamic boarding school which is located precisely at the Islamic boarding school, but not included officially in accordance with the registration of ha then followed by the responsibilities. This is also interpreted on the card owned by each member, obtaining mandatory savings. , principal and so on as well as obtaining the

right to make loans for types of goods and so on by each individual within the realm of the Islamic boarding school if they are included in a certain member section, while new students are reviewed based on the following year and experience changes from each -Each student who has graduated will be replaced by a new one, thus the membership system and the party carrying out the management will also continue to experience regular changes. *"One of the ways we ensure that this cooperative continues to run is that we consider all students as members, so anyone can join."*

c. Empowerment of Bookshop Santri Entrepreneurship

Entrepreneurship Empowerment of Bookshop Students, Empowerment of entrepreneurship in the bookshop sector is the same as other entrepreneurship, namely education and training. What is different in this field is related to the activities and sub-fields within it. The results of the interview with the students were "this bookshop sector is still running because the boarding school requires students to buy one of the textbooks in the bookshop, sis, and later the students are allowed to sell at a profit and keep it in the boarding house's treasury, usually if there are lots of books sold. *"We will give bonuses to students who have managed the bookshop."* Apart from that, there are also interview results delivered by the Ustad who said: *"If there are students who like to read, we also give them free book bonuses, so they don't bother paying for books, but this is like a reward for them."* Based on the results above, it can be said that the ust has given rewards to students who succeed in selling a large number of books, therefore the students are enthusiastic about participating in the bookshop program at the boarding school.

d. Entrepreneurship Empowerment of Manahij Resto Santri Students

Lastly, there are efforts to empower student entrepreneurship in the Manhij restaurant program. This field is very suitable for students who like cooking, in general the empowerment carried out is the same, namely education and training in each program, in this case the boarding school managers invite students to provide cooking training with new menus, for example morning menus and menus. evening, the training provided is also menus for patients who have certain diseases, not only that, Manahij Restaurant also opens catering which can be ordered by members of the public. In the results of his interview, the ustadzah stated: *"Here we give a lot of cooking training to santri, of course we don't just do theory, but before it is put into practice by the santri, usually the ustazah give examples or as models in cooking, after which they are imitated by the santri."*

DISCUSSION

Analysis of Research Data on Santri Entrepreneurship Empowerment Islamic boarding schools as Islamic scientific institutions! in everyday life it focuses on the importance of religious morals which are practiced as a guide to daily attitudes and behavior. The Manahjussadat modern Islamic boarding school in its teachings aims to prepare students to grow people who are useful and useful for the life around them. Based on this, the life of the Islamic boarding school is also very capable " to develop an entrepreneurial spirit for students in order to improve their welfare. The empowerment of students in the field of entrepreneurship began in 2017, precisely in February. This empowerment is based on the santri who have a simple life and are less able to meet their living needs while at the Islamic boarding school, therefore the leadership of the Manahjussadat modern Islamic boarding school has the desire that the santri can fulfill their needs with the results of their own efforts, so that the leadership of the Islamic boarding school has the determination to form a business entity owned by the students which is managed by the students and accompanied by one of the ustadz who is qualified to manage the entrepreneurship. Therefore, the leadership of the Manahjussadat Islamic boarding school initiated the formation of this entrepreneurship program. Meanwhile, the aim of Islamic boarding school leaders to form entrepreneurs is so that the students can be independent to meet their needs while at the boarding school and after the students are not living in the boarding school. Based on Soeharto's opinion, empowerment itself refers to the potential possessed by individuals or groups which are included in the weak aspect, so that overall they all have the ability to be obtained so that the needs they have can be fulfilled in a basic way, therefore the freedom that anan can use is essentially . Meanwhile, Payme said that empowerment itself is shown in reality by providing assistance to clients so that they can empower them in making policies that will be decided in accordance with the behavior implemented in relation to personal and can avoid various forms of challenges faced personally and socially when carrying out the actions in question.

To increase student productivity in entrepreneurship, of course there must be student enthusiasm first. This is because without enthusiasm within the students themselves, of course the product cannot continue to increase, therefore this Islamic boarding school prioritizes entrepreneurial values, one of which is by taking advantage of every opportunity that exists. Apart from cultivating a good entrepreneurial spirit, students are also required to be able to face challenges if there are challenges from the increasing number of consumer desires. So that students are more enthusiastic in carrying out their business, the ustadz always provides useful activities for entrepreneurs such as competitions for products made by the students themselves by giving prizes. quite large additional capital for the winner. This is in accordance with Bandura's theory (2017), namely that it can be seen that learning is a conscious effort carried out by humans through experience and practice to acquire new abilities and is a change in behavior that is relatively permanent." Based on this, the following are the results of research related to these efforts. The efforts that

have been made by the management of student entrepreneurship at the Manahijussadat Islamic Boarding School, the results of the research have been successfully grouped by researchers into the stages of Bandura theory (2017), the following are the results of the analysis:

1. Attention/Attention Stage

At this attention stage, namely seeking attention to the students to attract the attention of the students, at this stage the researcher makes a proposal to hold a special entrepreneurial activity whose aim is to invite students to take part in the entrepreneurship program held by the boarding school management. This activity involves *ustad gan ustadzah* as a model in the training program at the boarding school, only after that will the students follow and then apply it. Bandura's theory (2017) states that at this stage, before imitating someone else, attention must be paid to that person. This attention is influenced by the observer's association with the model, the attractive nature of the model, and the importance of the observed behavior for the observer.

2. Representation Stage

At this stage, researchers provide education about how to market products and then increase the number of goods purchased by consumers, so that buyers are not only from internal cottages but from consumers outside the cottage as well. This activity attracts student activities to be able to learn and make a profit from the products sold. This stage also tries to help students continue to remember what has been demonstrated in previous mentoring, not forgetting that there is mentoring in this process. According to Bandura's (2017) theory, representation is observing the model and then storing it in the form of symbols (not only obtained through visual observation, but also through which one day they are used in the form of imitating behavior).

3. Behavioral Production Stage

At this stage, the students immediately implement the products they will sell, as well as practice how to cook or sell, not only that, some students are starting to be interested in participating in the student entrepreneurship program because it can provide opportunities to make a profit, not only that, the number of sales sold at online platforms have increased because most bookings are from the cottages. The results of the interview revealed that the students liked this online sales medium because it could increase product sales turnover, although not many products were purchased from consumers outside the school. Bandura's theory (2017) states that this stage is the same as the implementation stage of training. In order to reproduce behavior correctly, a person must be able to demonstrate motor skills. Motor abilities include physical strength.

4. Motivation and Reinforcement Stage

At this stage, motivation and reinforcement are very necessary so that students remain consistent so that they can achieve their desired targets. At this

stage, the ustadz who manages the entrepreneurship program certainly has a role in continuing to provide encouragement to the students so that the students are always enthusiastic in applying what they have learned. Not only that, researchers also asked students regarding their sustainability in participating in this entrepreneurship program. Bandura theory (2017): Learning through observation is effective if the learner has high motivation to be able to carry out the model behavior. Observation may make it easier for people to master certain behavior, but if the motivation for it is not there, there will be no process of punished behavior. Imitation still occurs even if the model is not rewarded, long observers see the model has positive characteristics that are signs of a successful lifestyle, so it is believed that the model will generally be rewarded.

5. Research Findings

Based on the results of research that was carried out at the Manahijussadat Lebak Banten Modern Islamic Boarding School, the findings of the researchers were the empowerment of students in the field of boarding cooperatives, namely all that was done, among other things, was providing education and training. Before the students implement santri, they are given education related to activities in the field of cottage cooperatives. Not only that, the ustad also provides training to the students, in this training the ustaz continues to accompany the students and continues to provide direction to the students. The implementation of the stages for carrying out empowerment is based on the provision of training and begins with the preparation of the management team that has been formed, then knowing the level of business carried out by each group in accordance with its formation in a joint way in order to obtain increased legality. Kopontren membership itself is defined as each individual who is classified as a santri who is precisely in an Islamic boarding school but is not included in the rights or forms of obligations that should be carried out by Him officially, for example having a card as a member in this regard, providing savings in the nature of obligatory or basic and have rights to these aspects which are determined by each party who becomes a student within the scope of the domain in question and plays a role as a member, and there will be continuous changes, whether students who have graduated are replaced by new ones and the same goes for management abbreviation. . In theory, Bandura (2017) says that at this stage, before imitating another person, attention must be paid to that person. This attention is influenced by the observer's association with the model, the attractive nature of the model, and the importance of the observed behavior for the observer.

Empowerment of entrepreneurship in the bookshop sector is the same as other entrepreneurship, namely education and training. What is different in this field is that it is related to the activities and sub-fields within it. In this field, the boarding school policy is that it requires students to buy one study book every year, and gives awards to students who succeed in selling lots of books. Apart from that, the management also provides students with reading books for students who like to read, which is what makes this program popular with

students. At this stage, researchers provide education about how to market products and then increase the number of goods purchased by consumers, so that buyers are not only from internal cottages but from consumers outside the cottage as well. This activity attracts student activities to be able to learn and make a profit from the products sold. This stage also tries to help students continue to remember what has been exemplified in previous mentoring, not forgetting that there is mentoring in this process.

Empowerment of entrepreneurship in the Manahij restaurant sector means that there is education and training in each program, in this case the boarding school managers invite students to provide cooking training with new menus, for example morning menus and evening menus, while the training provided is also menus. For patients who have certain diseases, not only that, Manhij Restaurant also opens catering services that can be ordered by members of the public.

CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the research that has been carried out, it can be concluded:

1. Empowerment of student entrepreneurship in the field of Islamic boarding school cooperatives. Efforts made include providing education and training. Before the students implement *santi*, they are given education related to activities in the field of cottage cooperatives. Not only that, the *ustad* also provides training to the students, in this training the *ustad* continues to accompany the students and continues to provide direction to the students. The implementation of the stages for carrying out empowerment is based on the provision of training and begins with the preparation of the management team that has been formed, then knowing the level of business carried out by each group in accordance with its formation in a joint way in order to obtain increased legality. – *kopontren* membership itself is defined as each individual who is classified as a *santri* who is precisely in an Islamic boarding school but is not included in the rights or forms of obligations that should be carried out by Him officially, for example having a card as a member in this regard, providing savings which are mandatory or basic in nature and have rights to these aspects determined by each party who becomes a student within the scope of the domain in question and acts as a member. and there will be ongoing changes, whether students who have graduated are replaced by new ones and the same goes for the management abbreviations.

2. Empowerment of student entrepreneurship in the bookshop sector. In this field, the boarding school's policy is that it requires students to buy one study book every year, and gives awards to students who succeed in selling lots of books. Apart from that, the management also provides students with reading books for students who like to read, things - things That's what makes this program so popular with students,

3. Empowerment of student entrepreneurship in the manhij restaurant sector, namely the existence of education and training in each program, in this

case the boarding house managers invite students to provide cooking training with new menus, for example morning menus and evening menus, while the training provided is also menu- menu for patients who have certain diseases, not only that, Manhij Restaurant also opens catering which can be ordered by members of the public.

ADVANCED RESEARCH

Recommendations As the author has concluded above, the recommendations that would be useful for all parties are as follows:

1. For the facilitator, in this case the Manahijussadat Lebak Banten Modern Islamic Boarding School, namely: to continue to provide motivation and enthusiasm by holding sustainable training and coaching activities for the boarding school's students to continue to play an active role in participating in the entrepreneurship program at the boarding school. Apart from that, the entrepreneurship management and boarding school leaders as facilitating agents must have a special strategy for developing entrepreneurship programs.

2. For Santri, namely to continue to actively participate and increase entrepreneurial development, because if this entrepreneurship develops of course this is not only good for the boarding school but for themselves, it is hoped that the santri will maintain consistency.

ACKNOWLEDGMENT

Thank you to the Manahijussadat Modern Islamic Boarding School, and all those who have participated as the author has been permitted to research the research

REFERENCES

- Aprilia Theresia, et al. (2015). *Pembangunan Berbasis Masyarakat, Bandung Alfabeta.*
- Bandura, A. (1997). *Self Efficacy - The Exercise of Control (Fifth Printing, 2002). New York W.H. Freeman & Company.*
- Ghufron, & Risnawati. (2016). *Teori-teori Psikologi. Yogyakarta: Ar-Ruzz.*
- Karjuni Dt, Maani. (2018). *Teori Actor Dalam Pemberdayaan Masyarakat*
- Marzuki. (2005). *Metodologi Riset. Yogyakarta Ekonisia.*
- MuhammadAnwar. (2014). *Pengantar Kewirausahaan Teori dan Aplikasi. Jakarta Kencana.*
- Renaningtyas, W. (2017). *Terhadap Keberhasilan Usaha Pada Anggota. 5(4), 668-682.*